

**SpaceTeamSat1
Mechanical Design
Documentation**

21.05.2025

Version 1.0

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author(s)	Description
0.1	26.05.2024	Tim Munhowen	First Draft
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1 Introduction

This document aims to give an overview of the design of the mechanical structure carrying the electronics of the CubeSat mission SpaceTeamSat1 (STS1), which is led by the TU Wien Space Team [1]. The creation of the mechanical parts has gone through a lengthy development path starting in 2020 and ending in 2024. It has culminated in many different iterations of which only the final one is shown in this document.

In Section 1.1, the main properties of the CubeSat mission are briefly presented to establish the context of this document.

Next, the design philosophy followed during the development of the structure is outlined in Section 2.1. After that, the individual parts of the CubeSat are introduced. That subsection includes the used coordinate system, the naming conventions and the chosen material, as well as an in-depth look at each individual part. The requirements followed during the design of the CubeSat are presented in Section 3 and explanations are given regarding their fulfillment. The requirements are first based on the CubeSat Design Specification Rev. 14 (CDS) [2], but supplementary guidelines were also provided by our launch provider. The latter are not included in this document for reasons of confidentiality. Last, in Section 4.1 the technical drawings of the mechanical parts are presented.

1.1 Main properties of the CubeSat mission SpaceTeamSat1

In the following, the main properties of the CubeSat mission STS1 are recapitulated. They are directly taken from the critical design review of STS1 (CDR) [3]. For further information on the mission it is advised to visit the spaceteam website [4] or read the CDR [3].

- Mission and CubeSat name: SpaceTeamSat1 (short: STS1)
- 1U ($10 \times 10 \times 12 \text{ cm}^3$ approximately 1.1 kg) CubeSat platform
- STS1 shall operate in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) (350 km–500 km)
- STS1 shall be a lab for students of AHS and BHS
- STS1 shall enable access to the amateur radio community for students
- Educational mission objective:
 - Student teams compete in a space-related coding competition.
 - Python code which runs on the educational payload of the CubeSat (Raspberry Pi) platform.
 - Many possible software scenarios are possible. Therefore, various sensors are available for read-out.
 - Gathered data is handed over to participating students for further evaluation of the received data.
 - Student teams shall present their acquired results and therefore gain important insights into space-related technologies.
- The education module (EDU) with its sensors is the educational payload of the CubeSat:
 - Temperature sensor
 - Magnetometers
 - Accelerometers
 - Gyroscopes
 - Dosimeter
 - Brightness sensors
 - Cameras

2 Mechanical Design

2.1 Design Philosophy

The design philosophy behind the CubeSat's mechanical structure is guided by three core principles: simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and ease of manufacturability. These principles reflect the intention for the structure to be designed by students, for students, ensuring that the design remains accessible, practical, and suitable for educational environments.

One of the primary functions of the satellite's structure is to provide a secure platform for the onboard electronics, with sufficient structural integrity to endure the harsh environments encountered both during launch and later in space throughout the satellite's entire lifecycle.

The constraints of the design are set by the CubeSat Design Specification Rev. 14 [2] and complementary limitations set by our launch provider. These include the total dimensional design space, the choice of material, the weight, and many more parameters.

The structure of STS1 consists of six different parts: four sideplates, a top-plate and a bottom-plate. The main design idea is centered around the sideplates, which in their initial design are all close to identical. This has the advantage that for each sideplate a similar machining setup can be used. Furthermore, any lessons learned from a single part can be applied immediately to all the parts. Thus, in case of the top and bottom-plate, an effort is made to keep them as close as possible in design as well.

With the introduction of the onboard electronics, small alterations were required, and thus, as a result some parts diverged from others as they carry important features crucial for the functionality of the satellite (e.g. the deployment switch mechanism or the separation mechanism).

High priority is placed on the assembly process of the satellite. This means that the design chosen for the satellite allows for simple assembly and easy access to the electronic stack. This is, for example, demonstrated by the fact that only five parts of the spacecraft are required to keep the satellite's structural integrity intact. This means that the top or bottom plate can be removed without complication, a feature that is especially advantageous during assembly and testing procedures.

2.2 Coordinate System

For the proper identification of each part, the selection of a proper coordinate system is required. In Figure 2.1 below, two coordinate systems are displayed. The left one stems from the CDS document [2]; and was used in the initial design phases of the CubeSat, while the one on the right is the coordinate system requested by our launch provider, and thus chosen for our designs.

Note that for transforming the former into the latter, a rotation of 90° around the Y-axis accompanied by a rotation of 180° around the X-axis, is necessary.

Figure 2.1: (a): coordinate system used in the CDS guidelines [2].
(b): coordinate system used in the STS1 mission.

2.3 Naming Convention

The naming convention for each individual part of the CubeSat is a composition of two terms, and inherently linked to the coordinate system.

The name of a part is defined as follows:

1. CS stands for "CubeSat Structure"
2. "Xminus" refers to the direction in which the outwards facing side of the structure in its assembled state is oriented.

2.4 Material

The choice of material for spacecraft is critical, as it impacts the overall weight, the transmission of electromagnetic waves for communication, and the structural strength of the spacecraft.

For the CubeSat STS1, Aluminium 7075 was selected due to its formidable strength-to-weight ratio. Additionally, it is one of the materials recommended in the CDS guidelines [2].

The material properties of Al7075-T6 are given in Table 2.1 down below.

Physical properties	
Density	2.81 g/cm^3
Mechanical properties	
Young's Modulus	71700 MPa
Tensile Strength	572 MPa
Poisson ratio	0.33
Thermal properties	
Melting temperature	477 $^{\circ}C$
Thermal conductivity	130 – 150 $\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$
Linear thermal expansion coefficient	$2.36 \cdot 10^{-5} \frac{1}{K}$
Electrical properties	
Volume resistivity	51.5 $n\Omega \cdot m$

Table 2.1: Material properties of Al7075-T6

2.5 CubeSat Structures

In the following section the six parts:

- CS_Xplus ,
- CS_Xminus ,
- CS_Yplus ,
- CS_Yminus ,
- CS_Zplus ,
- CS_Zminus are presented.

More specifically, for each part, their distinct features are briefly outlined, figures are provided, and a table is given listing the screws connected to the structure.

To avoid repetition, a general remark is given which applies to each of the parts presented:

An extra set of M3 threaded holes is present on each of the parts. These do not contribute to the structural integrity of the spacecraft's assembly but provide possible fixation points during manufacturing and testing. They are specified in the technical drawings (Ergänzungszeichnung) of Section 4.1 page 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, and 13. Their purpose is to provide possible fixation points during manufacturing and testing.

2.5.1 CS_Xplus

CS_Xplus is the first structure presented. Following the naming convention, it is located on the positive X-side of the CubeSat assembly. Its role is to carry the Sidepanel_Xplus, a printed-circuit board (PCB) that carries two solar panels and the burning wire resistor mechanism, which is responsible for the deployment of the antennas. Additionally, CS_Xplus contains the deployment mechanism and the separation springs which play a crucial role during the payload ejection procedure. Together with CS_Xminus, CS_Xplus is responsible for carrying the electronic stack, done via four rods, which fit into the four cylindrical protrusions, shown in Figure 2.3.

Table 2.2 includes all the screws used to connect to CS_Xplus during the assembly.

Figure 2.2: View 1 of CS_Xplus

Figure 2.3: View 2 of CS_Xplus

Screw	Type	Head	Norm	Material	Attached to
M2 x 6	Countersunk Screw	Torx	TX ISO14581	Stainless Steel A2	
M2 x 8	Cylinder-head Screw	Torx	TX ISO14579	Stainless Steel A2	Side-PCB

Table 2.2: Screws attached to CS_Xplus

2.5.2 CS_Xminus

As suggested by its name, CS_Xminus, shown in Figures 2.4 and 2.5, is placed on the opposite side of CS_Xplus. It carries the Sidepanel_Xminus, i.e., the printed circuit board (PCB) to which the antenna is attached. Similar to its opposing counterpart, CS_Xplus, CS_Xminus guides the four rods that carry and center the electronic stack with the help of the four cylindrical protrusions shown in Figure 2.5.

Table 2.3 includes all the screws connecting to CS_Xminus during the assembly.

Figure 2.4: View 1 of CS_Xminus

Figure 2.5: View 2 of CS_Xminus

Screw	Type	Head	Norm	Material	Attached to
M2 x 6	Countersunk Screw	Torx	TX ISO14581	Stainless Steel A2	
M2 x 8	Cylinder-head Screw	Torx	TX ISO14579	Stainless Steel A2	Side-PCB

Table 2.3: Screws attached to CS_Xminus

2.5.3 CS_Yplus and CS_Yminus

Of all the structures covered in this section, CS_Yplus as well as CS_Yminus are the most complex, as they play a crucial role in the proper functioning of the deployment switch. For both structures, CS_Yplus and CS_Yminus, a wing-like feature is added to the rail (see figures 2.6, 2.7 and figures 2.8, 2.9). The function of that particular feature is to provide a surface onto which the deployment switch can be fixed.

Furthermore, as with the previous parts, the corresponding sidepanels, Sidepanel_Yplus and Sidepanel_Yminus are attached to them.

In both sideplates, a threaded hole is machined to accommodate a hysteresis rod. These rods are ferromagnetic bodies that serve to stabilize the spacecraft in case of unwanted rotational motion. For the CS_Yplus structure, the hysteresis rod is aligned with the Y-axis of the coordinate system, whereas in the CS_Yminus sideplate, the rod is aligned with the X-axis.

The screws used to connect both CS_Yplus and CS_Yminus are given in Table 2.4 and Table 2.5, respectively.

Figure 2.6: View 1 of CS_Yplus

Figure 2.7: View 2 of CS_Yplus

Screw	Type	Head	Norm	Material	Attached to
M2 x 6	Countersunk Screw	Torx	TX ISO14581	Stainless Steel A2	
M2 x 8	Cylinder-head Screw	Torx	TX ISO14579	Stainless Steel A2	Side-PCB

Table 2.4: Screws attached to CS_Yplus

2 Mechanical Design

Figure 2.8: View 1 of CS_Yminus

Figure 2.9: View 2 of CS_Yminus

Screw	Type	Head	Norm	Material	Attached to
M2 x 6	Countersunk Screw	Torx	TX ISO14581	Stainless Steel A2	
M2 x 8	Cylinder-head Screw	Torx	TX ISO14579	Stainless Steel A2	Side-PCB

Table 2.5: Screws attached to CS_Yminus

2.5.4 CS_Zplus

CS_Zplus, shown in Figure 2.10 and 2.11, is located on the positive Z-side of the assembly. It carries the Sidepanel_Zplus.

Its most notable feature is the threading for the last remaining hysteresis rod, i.e. the rod aligned with the Z-axis.

Table 2.6 includes all the screws connected to CS_Zplus when fully assembled.

Figure 2.10: View 1 of CS_Zplus

Figure 2.11: View 2 of CS_Zplus

Screw	Type	Head	Norm	Material	Attached to
M2 x 6	Countersunk Screw	Torx	TX ISO14581	Stainless Steel A2	
M2 x 8	Cylinder-head Screw	Torx	TX ISO14579	Stainless Steel A2	Side-PCB

Table 2.6: Screws attached to CS_Zplus

2.5.5 CS_Zminus

CS_Zminus, shown in Figure 2.12 and Figure 2.13, is placed on the negative Z-side of the CubeSat assembly. It primarily holds the Sidepanel_Zminus.

A 6 mm threaded hole is machined into an overhang feature at the front side of the plate. Its purpose is to fix the connector of the Remove-Before-Flight Pin to the structure.

On the negative X-side of the structure, another overhang is added. It touches the electronic stack and its purpose is to lead heat away from the electronic subcomponents.

Once more, Table 2.6 specifies all the screws that are connected to the part when the satellite is fully assembled.

Figure 2.12: View 1 of CS_Zminus

Figure 2.13: Render 2 of CS_Zminus

Screw	Type	Head	Norm	Material	Attached to
M2 x 6	Countersunk Screw	Torx	TX ISO14581	Stainless Steel A2	
M2 x 8	Cylinder-head Screw	Torx	TX ISO14579	Stainless Steel A2	Side-PCB

Table 2.7: Screws attached to CS_Zminus

3 Requirements

The development of the CubeSat structure is based on the CubeSat Design Specification Document [2], as required by our launch provider. The requirements and their fulfillment are noted down below. Note that, as a different coordinate system is used compared to that given in the official CDS requirements [2], both are mentioned in the requirement text. The coordinates in parentheses and marked in bold are the coordinates of our currently used coordinate system (i.e. the coordinate system presented in 2.2). Given the right transformation, they are equivalent to those of the CDS [2] guidelines.

3.1 Requirements CDS

1. The CubeSat shall use the coordinate system as defined in Appendix B. The origin of the CubeSat coordinate system is located at the geometric center of the CubeSat.

Fulfilled:

Not fulfilled, as we are using a custom coordinate system given by the launch provider. However, the cubesat was set up with the coordinate system given by the requirements and later a transformation of the coordinate system was applied, meaning that with the informations given in section 2.1b, a return to the CDS coordinate system can easily be achieved.

2. The CubeSat configuration and physical dimensions shall conform to Figure 3.1.

Fulfilled: ✓

Fulfilled as seen in the technical drawings of Section 4.1, page 1.

3. The $-Z$ ($+X$) face of the CubeSat will be inserted first into the dispenser.

Fulfilled: ✓

Shown in 4.1 Dimension Requirement Check pages.

4. No components on the yellow shaded sides (see Figure ?? CDS drawings) shall protrude farther than 6.5 mm normal to the surface from the plane of the rail.

Fulfilled: ✓

Shwon that it is fulfilled in document 3.2.

5. Deployables shall be constrained by the CubeSat, not the dispenser. This requirement originates from requirements of most Launch Providers.

Fulfilled: ✓

The only deployable in the STS1 Cubesat, are the antennas, which are constrained by the antenna deployment system.

6. Rails shall have a minimum width of 8.5mm measured from the edge of the rail to the first protrusion on each face.

Fulfilled: ✓

Shown that it is fulfilled in Document 3.2, page 2.

7. Rails should have a surface roughness less than 1.6 μm .

Fulfilled: ✓

A surface roughness of Ra 1.6 is defined on the rails. Shown in Document 4.1, page 1.

3 Requirements

8. The edges of the rails should be rounded to a radius of at least 1 mm.

Fulfilled: ✓

Shown in Document 4.1, page 1 - 13.

9. The ends of the rails on the +/- Z (+/- X) face shall have a minimum surface area of 6.5 mm x 6.5 mm contact area with neighboring CubeSat rails (as per drawing ?? in Appendix).

Fulfilled: ✓

Shown in document 4.1, page 2 and 4, as well as document 3.2, page 2.

10. At least 75% of the rail should be in contact with the dispenser rails. 25% of the rails may be recessed.

Fulfilled: ✓

Total surface area of the rails: 3121.52 mm² Rail surface area in contact with the deployer: 2851.52 mm² This means in the case of the STS1 Cubesat 91.35% are in contact with the dispenser, which is well over 75%.

11. Note: Table 1 shows the typical maximum mass for each U configuration.

Fulfilled: ✓

Table 3.1: Calculated data from the CAD Model on the 08.07.2024. The camera and antenna mass were not included, as they were still unknown at the time of measurement.

	Configuration	Mass [kg]
Requirement	1U	2.00
Measured		1.14088

12. The CubeSat center of gravity shall fall within the ranges specified in Table 3.2

Fulfilled: ✓

The Cubesat possesses the following center of gravity properties, shown in Table 3.2. The requirement is, therefore, fulfilled.

	Configuration	X-Axis	Y-Axis	Z-Axis
Requirement	1U	+ 2 cm / -2 cm	+2 cm / -2 cm	+2 cm / -2 cm
Measured		-0.460 cm	-0.036 cm	0.121 cm

Table 3.2

An additional requirement is the static unbalance for which the formula reads

$$(\sqrt{Y_{SC}^2 + Z_{SC}^2}) \quad (3.1)$$

Thus, the static unbalance properties of the CubeSat are given in Table 3.3.

Out of balance	Static Unbalance [mm]	Dyanmic Unbalance [°]
S/C Nominal	1.2624	Unknown

Table 3.3: Static Unbalance

3 Requirements

The moment of inertia is computed by the CAD program and given in Table 3.4. Here the positive tensor notation is used and the moment of inertia is calculated by using the center of mass as coordinate center.

Configuration	I_{XX} [kgm ²]	I_{YY} [kgm ²]	I_{ZZ} [kgm ²]
Measured	$2.212 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.073 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.080 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 3.4: Moment of Inertia measured from center of mass

As for the product of inertia, the data is given in Table 3.5 down below. Here, the positive tensor notation is used too, and the center of mass is used as coordinate center.

Configuration	P_{XY} [kgm ²]	P_{YZ} [kgm ²]	P_{ZX} [kgm ²]
Measured	$-1.549426 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-1.755929 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.257681 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Table 3.5: Product of Inertia using positive tensor notation (as in requirement) and measured from center of mass

13. The CubeSat structure should be made from aluminum alloy.

Fulfilled: ✓

The material chosen is Aluminium 7075.

14. Any aluminum CubeSat external surfaces, such as rails and standoffs that are in contact with the dispenser rails, shall be hard anodized to prevent any cold welding within the dispenser.

Fulfilled: ✓

Requested in drawings, see Document 4.1.

15. If a CubeSat shares a dispenser with another CubeSat(s), each CubeSat shall employ a mechanism to encourage separation from neighboring CubeSats within the dispenser.

Fulfilled: ✓

A separation spring mechanism is integrated in the -Z (+X) rails. See Section, where the mechanism is explained in detail.

16. The separation mechanism shall not extend beyond the level of the standoff in a stowed configuration.

Fulfilled: ✓

This is fulfilled by the nature of the design of the spring mechanism. For confirmation see Figure 2.1b.

3 Requirements

Figure 3.1: 1U CubeSat Dimensional Requirements. Taken and adjusted from CDS rev 14.1 [2]. The coordinate system in red is the coordinate system used for the STS1 mission.

Figure 3.2: Dimensional Requirements. Taken and adjusted from CDS rev 13 [5]. The coordinate system in red is the coordinate system used for the STS1 mission.

3.2 Requirement Check

The following section includes two drawings which serve as a visual aid to check if the given requirements are fulfilled. Furthermore, through the addition of the bill of materials, a simple overview of the assembled mechanical structure is given, helping with the identification of the individual parts during the assembly process.

ITEM NO.	PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	QTY.	Verantwortl. Abt.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch	Genehmigt von	Maßstab	
1	CS_Xplus		1	ST Mission	CAD-System: Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung: Dokumentenart Zeichnung Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Dimensional Requirements Check	Tim Munhowen	Material Al 7075	1:1	
2	CS_Zminus		1	STS1		Masse	Blattgröße A3		
3	CS_Zplus		1	Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 - f		Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle		
4	CS_Yplus		1			Zeichnungsnummer 1			
5	CS_Yminus		1			Version	Ausgabedatum 26.06.2024	Spr. GER	Blatt 1/2
6	CS_Xminus		1						

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ITEM NO.	Name	Beschreibung	QTY.	Verantwortl. Abt.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch	Genehmigt von	Maßstab
1	CS_Xplus		1	ST Mission	CAD-System: Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung:	Tim Munhowen		1:1
2	CS_Zminus		1	ST Mission		Material Al 7075		Blattgröße A3
3	CS_Zplus		1				Masse	Projektion First Angle
4	CS_Yplus		1				Dokumentenstatus	
5	CS_Yminus		1				Zeichnungsnummer 2	
6	CS_Xminus		1				Version	Ausgabedatum 26.06.2024
							Spr. GER	Blatt 2/2

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4 Technical Drawings

4.1 Technical Drawings of the CubeSat Structure

The following section includes the technical drawings which were used for the manufacturing of the structure of the CubeSat. Note that the drawings serve as complementary information to the .step files. They include the dimensional tolerances, surface roughness, and clarifications on the threaded holes.

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Alle bemaßten Bohrungen M3 dienen zur Fertigung.
M3 Bohrungen symmetrisch über die Mittelachsen.

Stück

1

Verantwortl. Abf.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab 1:1
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung: CS_Xplus	Material Al 7075 Masse	Blattgröße A3
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 - f	Dokumentenart Ergänzungszeichnung	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First angle	
	Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Bottom Plate (X+) Bohrungen Fertigung	Zeichnungsnummer 2B	Version 2	Ausgabedatum 30.07.2024 Spr. GER Blatt 3/13

Alle bemaßten Bohrungen M3 dienen zur Fertigung der Struktur.
M3 Bohrungen symmetrisch über die Mittelachsen.

Verantwortl. Abt.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab 1:1
ST Mission STS1	CAD-System: Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung:	CS_Xminus	Material Al 7075 Masse	Blattgröße A3
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 - f	Dokumentenart Ergänzungszeichnung	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle	
	Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Top Plate (X-) Bohrungen Fertigung	Zeichnungsnummer 3B	Version 2	Ausgabedatum 30.07.2024
				Spr. GER
				Blatt 5/13

Alle bemaßten Bohrungen M3 dienen zur Fertigung.

Verantwortl. Abt.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab 1:1
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung: CS_yminus	Material Al 7075 Masse	Blattgröße A3
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 -f	Dokumentenart Ergänzungszeichnung Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Side Plate (Y+) Bohrungen Fertigung	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle	
		Zeichnungsnummer 4B	Version 2	Ausgabedatum 30.07.2024

Alle bemaßten M3 Bohrungen dienen zur Fertigung,
sowie zur Befestigung an den Teststand.

Verantwortl. Abt.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab 1:1
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung: CS_Yminus	Material Al 7075 Masse	Blattgröße A3
Allgemeintoleranz ISO 2768 - f	Dokumentenart Ergänzungszeichnung	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle	
	Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Side Plate (Y-) Bohrungen Fertigung	Zeichnungsnummer 5B	Version 2	Ausgabedatum 30.07.2024 Spr. GER Blatt 9/13

Alle bemaßten Bohrungen M3 dienen zur Fertigung.

$\sqrt{Ra\ 3,2}$ ($\sqrt{Ra\ 1,6}$)

$\varnothing 5,5\ H7$	$\varnothing 5,512$	$\varnothing 5,500$
Toleranz	Größtmaß	Kleinstmaß

Verantwortl. Abt.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhownen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab 1:1
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung: CS_Zplus	Material Al 7075 Masse	Blattgröße A3
Allgemeintoleranz:		Dokumentenart Zeichnung	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle
ISO 2768 - f		Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Side Plate (Z+)	Zeichnungsnummer 6B	Version 2
			Ausgabedatum 30.07.2024	Spr. GER
				Blatt 11/13

Alle bemaßten Bohrungen M3 dienen zur Fertigung.

Verantwortl. Abt.	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch	Genehmigt von	Maßstab
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Dateinamen: Modell: Zeichnung: Solidworks 2021 CS_Zminus	Material Al 7075 Masse	Blattgröße A3
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 - f	Dokumentenart Ergänzungszeichnung Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Side Plate (Z-) Bohrungen Fertigung	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle	Zeichnungsnummer 7B
		Version 2	Ausgabedatum 30.07.2024	Spr. GER Blatt 13/13

SECTION D-D
SCALE 5 : 1

Stück
2

Verantwortl. Abt. Mechanics - STS1		Technische Referenz		Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen		Genehmigt von		Maßstab 5:1	
ST Mission STS1				CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: Deployment Stift Assembly Zeichnung:		Material Al 7075		Blattgröße A4	
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 - f		Dokumentenart Zeichnung		Dokumentenstatus		Masse		Projektion First Angle	
		Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Deployment Stift Assembly		Zeichnungsnummer 1		Version 1		Ausgabedatum 27.06.2024	
						Spr. GER		Blatt 1/3	

$\varnothing 4,0 f7$	$\varnothing 3,990$	$\varnothing 3,978$	
Toleranz	Größtmaß	Kleinstmaß	Stück 2

Verantwortl. Abt. Mechanics - STS1	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab 5:1
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: Stift Zeichnung:	Material Al 7075	Blattgröße A4
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 -f		Dokumentenart Zeichnung - Einzelteil	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle
	Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Stift	Zeichnungsnummer 2	Version 1	Ausgabedatum 27.06.2024
				Blatt 2/3

SECTION E-E

Stück
2

Verantwortl. Abt. Mechanics - STS1	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab	
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: DeploymentSwitchKopf Zeichnung:	Material Al 7075	Blattgröße A4	
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 - f		Dokumentenart Zeichnung - Einzelteil	Dokumentenstatus	Projektion First Angle	
	Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Kopfteil	Zeichnungsnummer 3	Version 1		

$\varnothing 3,00 f7$	$\varnothing 2,994$	$\varnothing 2,984$	Stück 2
$\varnothing 4,00 f7$	$\varnothing 3,990$	$\varnothing 3,978$	
Toleranz	Größtmaß	Kleinstmaß	

Verantwortl. Abt. Mechanics - STS1	Technische Referenz	Erstellt durch Tim Munhowen	Genehmigt von	Maßstab 10:1
ST Mission STS1		CAD-System: Solidworks 2021 Dateinamen: Modell: Huelse_SepSpring Zeichnung:	Material Al 7075	Blattgröße A4
Allgemeintoleranz: ISO 2768 - f		Dokumentenart Zeichnung - Einzelteil	Dokumentenstatus	Masse
	Titel, Zusätzlicher Titel Huelse - Separation Spring	Zeichnungsnummer 1	Version 1	Ausgabedatum 25.06.2024
				Spr. GER
				Blatt 1/1

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